

Is Urine Source Separation the Environmentally Preferred Option for Wastewater Management? Insights from a Life Cycle Assessment Study

H. Appiah-Twum^{*, **}, T. Van Winckel^{*, ****}, J. Santolin^{*}, J. De Paepe^{*}, S. Hellweg^{***}, T.A. Larsen^{****}, K. M. Udert^{***, ****}, S. E. Vlaeminck^{*, ****}, M. Spiller^{*, **}

^{*}Biobased Sustainability Engineering (SUSTAIN), Department of Bioscience Engineering, University of Antwerp, Groenenborgerlaan 171, 2020 Antwerpen, Belgium

^{**}VITO Water, Wetenschapspark 1, 8400, Oostende, Belgium

^{***}Institute of Environmental Engineering, ETH Zurich, CH-8093 Zurich, Switzerland

^{****}Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology, (EAWAG), Überlandstrasse 133, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland

^{*****}Centre for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Frieda Saeynsstraat 1, 9052 Gent, Belgium

(Email: Hanson.Appiah-Twum@uantwerpen.be)

Abstract

This study evaluates the environmental impact of hybrid wastewater treatment systems, which combine decentralized urine treatment with a highly efficient centralized WWTP with low nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and electricity use. The comparison is made against the impact of the same centralized WWTP treating mixed wastewater. The results show that the hybrid scenarios showed a lower impact than the baseline in marine, freshwater eutrophication and marine, freshwater ecotoxicity. However, all the hybrid scenarios presented a higher global warming impact than the baseline scenario. A sensitivity analysis on direct N₂O emissions and centralized WWTP electricity use shows that while urine source separation is not preferred to a highly efficient WWTP, it can be used to improve the global warming impact of less efficient WWTPs.

Keywords

Environmental assessment; greenhouse gas emissions; resource recovery; wastewater management

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the objectives of wastewater treatment have shifted towards resource recovery, energy neutrality, and reducing the impact of climate change. Specifically, in the EU, the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive is being updated to include stringent measures all geared towards the EU green deal (European Commission, 2022). These evolving guidelines pose challenges for wastewater treatment plants, demanding innovative solutions.

An emerging solution is the treatment of source-separated urine, which constitutes less than 1% of wastewater volume but contains 80% nitrogen and 50% phosphorus (Larsen & Gujer, 1996). Hybrid systems combining urine separation with centralized black and grey water treatment have been proposed to reduce nutrient loads and improve overall system performance.

Previous studies suggest that urine source separation and treatment present a lower environmental impact than conventional WWTPs through life cycle assessments (LCA) (Besson et al., 2021). However, there is currently no LCA study on partial nitrification and a combined struvite precipitation with ammonia stripping in a hybrid system compared to conventional WWTPs. The importance of the characteristics of centralized WWTPs, where grey and blackwater are treated, has been highlighted in previous environmental assessment studies. Most comparisons involve WWTPs with high energy use and N₂O emissions, though these values can vary significantly (De Haas & Andrews, 2022). Given the significance of these parameters, it is essential not only to compare innovative urine source treatment technologies with highly efficient WWTPs, but also to determine the N₂O emissions at which urine source separation results in a lower impact.

To fulfil these knowledge gaps, this study aims to conduct a consequential LCA to compare three urine treatment systems (partial nitrification & distillation, partial nitritation/anammox and struvite

precipitation & stripping/scrubbing) to a highly efficient central WWTP.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The environmental impact of the three decentralized urine treatment systems combined with a highly efficient centralized WWTP (hybrid system) in a Swiss city with a population equivalent (PE) of 189,000. The comparison is made against the environmental performance of the same centralized WWTP (baseline) treating an equivalent PE of mixed wastewater. Eight impact categories were assessed using the ReCiPe 2016 midpoint (H) method.

An 80% urine source separation efficiency was assumed, with 20% of the nitrogen load from urine directed to the centralized WWTP. The remaining untreated urine was transferred with greywater, brown water, and urine treatment effluent to the central WWTP. A fictitious city was designed, which features seven-story residential buildings, each housing 400 people (2.2 PE per dwelling). Urine was collected and treated in clusters of 1,200 PE, with treatment facilities located in the basement of one building and connected to two others via 50m drainage pipes. The entire population was assumed to use source-separating toilets with dedicated urine piping, resulting in 158 decentralized systems linked to the central WWTP in hybrid scenarios.

A consequential LCA was performed using a functional unit of 1 PE of wastewater treated per day, ensuring compliance to Switzerland's legal effluent discharge limits: 45 g/m³ chemical oxygen demand (COD), 0.8 g/m³ total phosphorus (P), 60% total nitrogen (N) removal, 2 g/m³ ammonium (NH₄⁺), 0.3 g/m³ nitrite (NO₂⁻), and 20 g/m³ total suspended solids. In this study, 1 PE/day is defined based on nutrient loads as 12.9 g N, 1.6 g P, and 136 g COD. The system boundary includes urine collection, treatment, fertilizer transportation to fields, and centralized wastewater treatment.

The life cycle inventory (LCI) of the baseline WWTP was based on a 365-day average of primary data from a highly efficient WWTP. A steady-state model of the centralized WWTP was created from the primary data using SUMO software. A calibrated model was generated and then used to simulate changes in influent composition resulting from urine source separation. To comply with the effluent discharge limits, adjustments were made to the aeration model, blower efficiency, air input, and chemical dosing. The simulation results provided LCI data for the hybrid central WWTP. Data for the urine treatment systems were based on primary, literature and manual calculations.

The assessment used various direct GHG emission factors for the treatment systems. For the central WWTP, an N₂O emission factor (EF) of 0.4% of influent nitrogen (N) (primary data) and methane EFs of 0.1% and 0.9% of influent COD (Gruber, 2021) were applied for activated sludge and sludge management, respectively. For urine treatment systems, an N₂O EF of 1.5% of influent N (Faust et al., 2022) was used for the partial nitrification & distillation system, and 1.8% of influent N (Diezinger et al., 2023) for the partial nitrification/anammox systems.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From **Figure 1A**, it can be concluded that urine source separation increases the electricity use of wastewater treatment. The gross electricity demand of the central WWTP is 0.059 kWh/PE/day with aeration for nutrient removal in the activated sludge process, accounting for approximately 33% of this amount. Electricity production from the digestion of sludge, fats, and grease results in a net negative electricity balance. The net electricity balance of the hybrid scenarios is 87 to 265 times higher than the baseline, primarily due to the electricity demand for urine treatment.

Urine source separation led to higher NH₄⁺ concentrations in the hybrid scenarios (Figure 1B). An 80% urine separation resulted in high COD/N ratios in the influent to the central WWTP, which favoured the growth of heterotrophic organisms over nitrifiers, leading to reduced NH₄⁺ oxidation

and higher NH_4^+ effluent levels. The hybrid scenarios had lower NO_2^- and NO_3^- concentrations due to decreased nitrification activity.

The LCA results (**Figure 2**) show that the hybrid scenarios showed a lower impact than the baseline in marine, freshwater eutrophication and marine, freshwater ecotoxicity. However, all the hybrid scenarios presented a higher global warming impact than the baseline scenario. While most studies conclude that urine source separation systems have a lower global warming impact than conventional WWTPs, this study suggests that a urine source separation system is not preferred to a highly efficient central WWTP.

The contribution analysis on global warming impact (**Figure 3**) shows that a reduced urine load to the central WWTP in the hybrid scenarios decreased the central WWTP's global warming impact by up to 33%. However, the impact of urine treatment, dominated by N_2O emissions and increased electricity use, caused the overall impact of the hybrid to exceed the baseline.

A sensitivity analysis on direct N_2O emissions show that using N_2O EFs from IPCC (2019) and De Haas & Andrews (2022), 87% of the centralized WWTPs had lower CO_2 emissions compared to partial nitrification & distillation, and 91% compared to partial nitrification/anammox hybrid solutions. However, at a centralized WWTP energy demand of 1 kWh/PE/day and 1.5 kWh/PE/day, both hybrid solutions showed lower emissions than all the WWTPs.

CONCLUSION

This study compared three hybrid wastewater treatment systems that combine decentralized urine treatment with a highly efficient centralized WWTP to the same central WWTP treating mixed wastewater. The main conclusions are:

- The hybrid scenarios had a lower impact than the baseline in six out of eight categories, except for global warming and marine eutrophication.
- While urine source separation reduces nutrient loads to the central WWTP, the hybrid systems increase electricity use and GHG emissions.
- The findings suggest that while urine source separation is not preferred to a highly efficient WWTP, it can be used as a strategy to improve the global warming impact of less efficient WWTPs.

REFERENCES

- Besson, M., Berger, S., Tiruta-barna, L., Paul, E., & Spérandio, M. (2021). Environmental assessment of urine, black and grey water separation for resource recovery in a new district compared to centralized wastewater resources recovery plant. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 301, 126868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126868>
- De Haas, D., & Andrews, J. (2022). Nitrous oxide emissions from wastewater treatment—Revisiting the IPCC 2019 refinement guidelines. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2022.100557>
- Dieziger, C., Freimann, R., Durisch-Kaiser, E., & Joss, A. (2023). Lachgasemissionen aus Faulwasserbehandlung. Beprobung und Einordnung 12 Schweizer Anlagen.
- European Commission. (2022). *Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning Urban Wastewater Treatment*. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:fc078ec8-55f7-11ed-92ed-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
- Faust, V., Gruber, W., Ganigué, R., Vlaeminck, S. E., & Udert, K. M. (2022). Nitrous Oxide Emissions and Carbon Footprint of Decentralized Urine Fertilizer Production by Nitrification and Distillation. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestengg.2c00082>
- Gruber, W. J. (2021). *Long-term N_2O emission monitoring in biological wastewater treatment: Methods, applications and relevance* [ETH Zurich]. https://www.dora.lib4ri.ch/eawag/islandora/object/eawag%3A24570/datastream/PDF/Gruber-2021-Long-term_N2O_emission_monitoring_in-%28published_version%29.pdf

Larsen, T. A., & Gujer, W. (1996). Separate management of anthropogenic nutrient solutions (human urine). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1223\(96\)00560-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0273-1223(96)00560-4)

Figure 1 Electricity use (A) and effluent nitrogen concentrations (B) of the studied scenarios

Figure 2 Impact of the hybrid scenarios relative to the baseline. An impact above 1 indicates a higher impact than the baseline while an impact below 1 indicates a lower impact than the baseline

Figure 3 Contribution analysis of the studied scenarios' impact on global warming